

TECHNOLOGIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF INITIATIVITY AT STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10227625>

Abstract. *The article notes that the quality of education in developed countries is determined by the level of initiative of the staff, the level of development of its innovative and creative activity, the practice of developing entrepreneurial abilities of students based on socio-psychological trainings, business games, television shows, debates in South Korea, China is also widespread. Russia, Germany and France, including reforms in the education system, are focused on issues of developing entrepreneurship in the future, improving mechanisms for their development creativity. Along with the foregoing, the article focuses on the sociological and anthropological components and ethno-regional factors of entrepreneurship development, the national mentality and principles of social partnership as a result of global research on entrepreneurship development.*

Keywords: *to the sociological and anthropological components, intellectually developed, self-organization, openness, non-linearity, no equilibrium, bifurcation, fluctuation, dissipative structures, attractor.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the developed countries of the world, the quality of education is determined by the level of development of the skills of initiative personnel, their innovative, creative activity. In particular, in countries such as South Korea, China, Russia, Germany, France, the development of students' initiative on the basis of socio-psychological trainings, business games, television programs, debates has been studied and put into practice. Based on the internationalization of the educational process, priority is given to the preparation of competitive, creative, initiative personnel in socio-economic and intercultural relations.

In the world, Promising areas of scientific and pedagogical research are gaining importance in expanding pedagogical and psychological opportunities that develop professional initiative in future personnel, and in researching the design of a culture of initiative in them. Five important initiatives have been put forward in our republic aimed at attracting young people to culture and art, physical education and sports, using computer technology and the Internet, reading fiction, and increasing the social activity of girls. In addition, the country's legal system has updated the legal framework for improving the mechanisms for training competitive personnel, and created the material and technical infrastructure. "Road maps" have been developed for the strategic development of higher educational institutions, and joint faculties and university branches are being organized, together with leading higher educational institutions of foreign countries. Reforms in the education system serve the development of initiative among future personnel, and improve the mechanisms for developing their creative potential.

In the Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Increasing the social activity of youth in the process of deepening democratic reforms and developing civil society, organizing effective activities of state authorities and administration, educational institutions, youth and other organizations in the implementation of state youth policy" [Journal "People's words" 2017] identified as priority tasks. As a result, ample opportunities have been

created for the development and implementation in practice of a pedagogical strategy for the development of initiative in students of technical higher educational institutions.

Research related to the development of student initiative is carried out in leading scientific centers and higher educational institutions of the world, including The center of social sciences in Seoul national university (South Korea), Moscow State University (Russia), New York City Leadership Academy (USA), Hamburg University in Germany (Germany), University of Sorbonne (France), National Foundation for Educational Research (UK), University of South Australia (Australia), Nagoya university (Japan) [Kadyrova R.M. et al., 2005, 2007, 2009, 1981].

II. THE MAIN PART: In the world for the development of students' initiative, research is being carried out in the following priority areas: improving pedagogical mechanisms for ensuring cooperation between state and non-governmental organizations in the development of students' initiative development of educational technology for the development of initiative among students; improving the conceptual framework for the development of initiative in students; improving the socio-pedagogical diagnostic apparatus and a set of methods for the development of initiative in students

The peoples living in Central Asia considered the hardworking people to be good, cultivating such qualities as high morality, chastity, modesty, kindness, i.e. the entire family had the same requirements as the individual. Thus, the perfection of the individual grew into the perfection of the family (collective), the perfection of the family into the perfection of the tribe, and it already led to the perfection of the people as a single and great collective of fighters for the right to a worthy life [Volkov G.N. et al., 2000].

The virtues and their opposites include: the mind, it is clouded by irritation, bitterness; friendship, envy ruins her; conscience, greed destroys it; good upbringing, but it can be affected by a bad environment; modesty, licentiousness harms her; kindness, selfishness prevents her; happiness, jealousy destroys him [Andriyanova V.I. 2008. Part 1. p.p. 64-72]. At present, education, in its qualitative characteristic, is not only a value, system or process, but also a result, fixing the fact of appropriation by the state, society, and personality of all those values that are born in the process of educational activity, which are so important for economic, moral, the intellectual state of the educational sphere - the state, society, each person, the entire civilization as a whole [Gershunsky B.S. 2003.– 765 p].

The main ideas and principles of educating the young generation are reflected in the works of the great thinkers of the past, encyclopedic scientists of Central Asia and the East: Abu Nasr al-Ferrari, Abu Rackham Bruin, Abu Ali Bin Siena, Yusuf Khos-Khojib, Ahmad Mugnai, Jalaliddin Divine Alisher Navai and many others According to the results of the study, the development of initiative in students requires the introduction and harmonization of a variety of approaches in the educational process. Based on the analyzes, a technology has been developed for introducing cultural-humanistic, synergetic, hermeneutic approaches to developing students' initiative (Fig. 1). [Ismailova Z. et al. 2019. - p.p.734-751].

The unity of the word, pattern and practice requires the development of initiative among students. The formative influence should serve to ensure sustainable organization mechanisms and the development of student initiative resources, as well as behavior management. Based on the results of the study, we came to the conclusion that the technology for developing initiative in students should be based on the behavior model “show an example - explain - train”.

The teacher presents students with a model for mastering initiative, their assessment, reflection of their attitude, as well as perception as a criterion of personal behavior. The technology of developing initiative in students serves to control the student's behavior: it stimulates socially positive actions and reduces socially negative effects. It is for this reason that in the model of behavior development of initiative among students, the introduction of an assessment, score and competition elements is of great importance.

Fig 1. Technologies for the development of initiative in students

III. DISCUSSION

By a personality-oriented approach it is customary to understand a methodological orientation in pedagogical activity, which allows relying on a system of interconnected concepts, ideas and methods of action to ensure and support the processes of self-knowledge, self-construction and self-realization of a person, the development of his unique individuality. This definition reflects the essence of this approach and its most important aspects are highlighted:

firstly, a personality-oriented approach is, first of all, an orientation in pedagogical activity; secondly, it is a comprehensive education consisting of concepts, principles and methods of pedagogical actions; thirdly, this approach is associated with the aspirations of the teacher to promote the development of the student's individuality, the manifestation of his subjective qualities [Yuzlikayeva E.R. 2007. - 188 p].

Three components of this approach:

1. The basic concepts that, when implementing pedagogical actions, are the main tool of thought activity. Their absence in the consciousness of the teacher or the distortion of their meaning makes it difficult or even impossible to consciously and purposefully apply the orientation in question in pedagogical activity:

The basic concepts of a personality-oriented approach, in our opinion, include the following:

- individuality - a unique identity of a person or group, a unique combination of individual, species and common features that distinguishes them from other individuals and human communities;

- personality - a constantly changing systemic quality, manifested as a stable set of properties of the individual and characterizing the social essence of man; self-actualized personality - a person who consciously and actively realizes the desire to become himself, to fully reveal his abilities and abilities;

- self-expression - the process and result of the development and manifestation by an individual of his inherent qualities and abilities;

- subject - an individual or group possessing conscious and creative activity and freedom in cognition and transformation of himself and the surrounding reality;

- subjectivity - the quality of an individual person or group, reflecting the ability to be an individual or group subject and expressed by the measure of possessing activity and freedom in the choice and implementation of activities;

- Self-concept - a system of self-awareness that is realized and experienced by a person about himself, on the basis of which he builds his life activity, interaction with other people, relationships with himself and others; choice - the exercise by a person or group of the opportunity to choose from a combination of the most preferred option for the manifestation of their activity;

- pedagogical support - the activities of teachers to provide preventive and operational assistance to children in solving their individual problems related to physical and mental health, communication, successful promotion in learning, life and professional self-determination.

2. The starting points and basic rules of building the process of training and education of students. Let us call the principles of a personality-oriented approach: the principle of self-actualization, individuality, subjectivity, choice, creativity and success; principle of trust and support.

3. The technological arsenal of the personality-oriented approach is made up of methods and techniques that meet such requirements as: dialog city and creative activity [Umansky L.I. 2001. - 160 p]. With the development of initiative, students should argue for a synergistic approach that requires consideration of the unity of non-linear action, randomness and external influences of this process [Babakhodjaeva L.G. 2009 .-- 20 p].

The results of the study showed that with the development of initiative students do not have continuous stability, and this requires the need to rely on strategies for modeling educational situations, providing feelings, motives, relationships of subjects of the educational process.

We define the synergetic approach as a post-neoclassical interdisciplinary line of research on open no equilibrium and non-linear systems in order to study the processes of self-organization and self-development of social and natural phenomena. The main concepts of synergetic are “self-organization”, “openness”, “non-linearity”, “no equilibrium”, “bifurcation”, “fluctuation”, “dissipative structures”, “attractor”. Self-organization is a process or set of processes occurring in a system, contributing to the maintenance of its optimal functioning, contributing to the self-building, self-healing and self-modification of a given systemic education; pennies is a property of the system due to the presence of communication channels with the external environment for the exchange of matter, energy and information; non-linearity - this is the presence of a system of many options, including alternative, possible development paths and ways of system responses to external influences; no equilibrium is the quality of a system located far from the equilibrium state; bifurcation (translated from Latin means "bifurcation") – it is a branching of the paths of evolution (development) of an open nonlinear system; fluctuation (translated from the Latin language means “fluctuation”) is a random deviation (change) of the quantities characterizing the system from their average values, leading under certain conditions to the formation of a new structure and system quality, i.e. to the emergence of a new system; this is a relatively finite, stable state of the system, which, as it were, attracts the whole set of “trajectories” of movement (development) of a system object [Philosophy obrazovaniya XXI veka. 1992. - 178 p].

Also, the results of the study made it possible to come to the conclusion that with a synergistic approach to the development of initiative in students, if the mutually educational influence departs from the point of choice (bifurcation), then purely external, quantitative changes occur in the behavior and activities of students. And the intermediate, instant pedagogical impact, consonant with the freedom of choice of students, can lead to a sharp change in the motivational and value-oriented sphere of activity, in this process it is advisable to give the subject the freedom of choice of action. With the development of initiative in students, it is necessary to pay special attention to the internal potential of individual activity. Therefore, the pedagogical influence must take into account the nonlinear, random actions of the pupil in the process of self-awareness, adapt with natural actions and a high degree of activity. From the hermeneutic point of view, the development of initiative in students is directly related to the psychological experiences of the subject, manifesting in the form of experiences, turning to his inner world. The results of the study show the need for the assimilation of mental experiences through reflection, the service of the reaction of behavior, the subject of the development of initiative in students.

The processes of change are growing with tremendous speed in all spheres of human activity, including in the educational system and in professional activities. In this context, the integrative function of hermeneutics will ensure not only adequate perception and actualization of these changes, but also mediate the experience of trans-cultural traditions of world education. The use of hermeneutic methods of interpretation and understanding is becoming especially important in the context of modern scientific reality, where generally valid values have not yet been finally formed.

Based on the vast historical and cultural experience, hermeneutics will allow avoiding the traditional formulation of scientific problems, and, therefore, develop a different interpretation

strategy, develop other technical procedures. As history shows, thanks to hermeneutics, such currents as the critical theory of society or so important for the study of strategies of science, culture and education as structural-semiotic analysis have become actualized.

A review of hermeneutical principles developed during the historical development of hermeneutical theory gives reason to argue that there are two completely different understandings of hermeneutics. The first focuses on the objectivity of the humanities, but at the same time tries to preserve the individual identity of its objects - it belongs to the classical (romantic, reproductive, reproducing, historical) hermeneutics. The second rejects the concept of the method and objectivity of the cultural sciences and focuses on the very possibility of understanding. It belongs to hermeneutics fundamental (philosophical, modern, ontological, integrative) [Zakirova A.F. 2001. - 152 p].

A vertical (historical) comparative analysis of the conceptual apparatus of hermeneutics showed that classical hermeneutics is a methodology of the humanities. Moreover, the study of the triad is essential for the process of understanding: the subject - the method of understanding - the subject. In modern hermeneutics, the subject of knowledge is called a hermeneutic or an interpreter, and the subject of hermeneutics is called an *interprendum*.

The object of hermeneutics is understood as any manifestation of human culture, regardless of their specific form. The theory of hermeneutics abstracts from them, it does not matter to her whether it is about texts, paintings, buildings or about human behavior and actions, although, undoubtedly, we can and should talk about the hermeneutics of the text, hermeneutics of music, architecture, etc. Traditionally, The subject area of hermeneutics included, first of all, history, language, art, religion, law, customs and educational systems, that is, symbolic systems and structures of everyday life. These are mainly those subjects that are studied and dealt with in the framework of humanitarian knowledge during the 19th and 20th century.

Turning to a horizontal comparative analysis of the essence of the hermeneutic approach, it should be noted that with respect to any object of study it should be characterized by the triad "interdisciplinary - transdisciplinarity - multidisciplinary". "Transdisciplinarity" characterizes hermeneutics as a scientific methodology, research, in which various disciplines go "through" and "through" and go to a higher level, a meta level that is independent of a particular discipline [Ismailova Z. Et al..2019.1175 p].

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One of the founders of the hermeneutic approach in pedagogical research is the Tyumen Academic School of Pedagogy, headed by academician V.I. Zagvyazinsky. She specified the hermeneutic approach in pedagogical science at the level of conceptual use of A.F. Zaire, who introduced the term "pedagogical hermeneutics". By pedagogical hermeneutics, the author

understands the theory and practice of interpreting and interpreting pedagogical knowledge, recorded in various written texts and reflecting ideas about pedagogical reality (a person as a subject of creative self-development, goals, mechanisms, principles, content, methods and forms of upbringing and self-education), with the goal of the most complete understanding and deep understanding of this knowledge, taking into account socio-cultural traditions, reflective understanding of the emotional and spiritual experience of a person society and personal spiritual experience of the subject of understanding [Batarshv A.V. 1999 .-- 176 p].

IV.CONCLUCIONS.

It should be noted that in recent years the education system has undergone a number of significant changes, therefore the support in the hermeneutic understanding only of texts and knowledge recorded textually is insufficient, because the informatization processes of the education system make it possible to speak not only about the text, but about information in general, which, in our opinion, is becoming an important resource of any education, any pedagogical technology. From this point of view, one should speak not about the hermeneutic approach, but about the hermeneutic technology in the learning process [Ismailova Z. K., - 2015. - No. 8. – p.p. 800-801].

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In the application of hermeneutic technologies of education in the development of initiative in students, it is necessary to pay special attention to the activation of their inner experiences, memories, imaginations, wishes and goals. In this situation, it is advisable for the teacher to perceive the students' verbal creativity as a system of individual values with initiative abilities. With the development of initiative in students on the basis of the hermeneutic approach, they came to the conclusion that it is necessary to take into account their awareness in the essence of life, the full manifestation of individuality

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